

COMPASSION OF PROVISION OF LEARNING RESOURCES FOR SPECIAL NEEDS EDUCATION PUPILS IN SELECTED PUBLIC PRIMARY SCHOOLS IN KAKAMEGA COUNTY, KENYA

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Abstract:

The conceptual frame was used in a study which sought to investigate the achievement of equity in the provision of Physical Education learning resources to physically challenged and typical learners in inclusive schools. The importance of the conceptual framework is to sensitize the stakeholders, education administrators, staffing officers, learners, Parents and the community on how quality education could easily be achieved through provision of appropriate learning resources in an inclusive setting. The problem of lack of conducive learning environment for challenged learners in inclusive settings has been echoed in many reports. The main objective of making the conceptual framework is to help the educators be in a position to use appropriate resources in an inclusive setting to achieve a meaningful education. The conceptual framework uses ideas from the Resource Dependence Theory and Social Development Theories. The theories were utilized to address the key issues in the study. The Resource Dependence Theory which sees organizations to be dependent on resources in their environment and succeed by maximizing on their power to compete and utilize those resources. On the other hand, the Social Development Theory argues that every function in the child's cultural development appears twice: first on the social level and later on the individual level, first between people (Inter-psychology) and later inside the child (Intra-psychology). This applies equally to voluntary attention, logical memory and formation of concepts.

Keywords: resources, actualization, intervention, curriculum, flexibility

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1. Conceptual Framework

The conception framework was developed by the researcher to investigate the provision of school learning environment, teachers and their suitability for the learning of physically challenged and typical learners. The conceptual situation calls for a conducive environment which includes curriculum, appropriate facilities and resources, school and classroom requirements. The teacher related factors are: professional qualifications, individual learners with special needs and methods of instructions. The school learning environment and teacher could affect the learning of the physically challenged or typical learners either positively or negatively. Special need students as a result of physical and social barriers are experiencing problems in accessing quality education. However if intervention is done to remove the barriers there is a possibility that access problems facing this group of learners will not be an issue in inclusive schools. The conceptual framework is important in assessing the methodology and learning expectation of the pupils.

Figure 1: Kidiga’s equation model: Relationship between Factors That Facilitate Acquisition of Knowledge and Skills and Inclusion of P.C.L

Source: Developed by the research based on ideas from Social Development Theory and Resource Dependence Theory (Kidiga's equation model). Figure 1 shows the relationship of factors that make S.N.E learners be locked out of or be accommodated in learning institutions. Improper utilization of these factors lessens their opportunities in accessing quality education. Due to physical and social factors to the school, teachers and cultural factors as seen in the diagram, may account for their accommodation or exclusion. The nature or the situation of such factors in any given school would either support or oppose inclusion. It is only through inclusion that such factors could be adjusted to overcome the inclusion problem. There is need for the right intervention for this to succeed. Once such intervention is done, then discrimination and segregation would be a dream. Such interventions would create equal opportunities through provision of suitable resources and facilities to all learners in such schools. Suitable learning resources will only be achieved if there is positive utilization of the relationships shown in the figure. When positive utilization of the relationship has been utilized, the path to right intervention will have been opened. The right intervention will lead to a variety of opportunities which previously they were denied. Once such opportunities are created, the learner will easily be assimilated by the society. This will lead him or her to have the opportunity for self-actualization and self-reliance which will make him or her to be accepted in the society.

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